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Telomerase control of Xist through Trf2.

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We demonstrated control of Xist non-coding RNA activation by the BRCA1/tp53bp1 DNA damage signaling system containing NBS complex component MRE11A and a factor important for maintenance of the telomeres, *Rif1*. We describe here identification of a second telomerase-associated component important and sufficient for Xist activation in human cells, *Trf2*.